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Prevalence and Determinants of Frailty:

A Cross-Sectional Study from Rural and Urban Communities in South Lebanon

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KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

Frailty is a common geriatric syndrome that poses an increased risk of catastrophic declines in health and functional impairment in older adults. Frailty is a condition associated with aging that has been recognized for centuries. Despite gaining global attention, determinants of frailty have remained unmeasured in rural/urban community settings in Lebanon. This study aimed to identify this gap by assessing the prevalence and determinants of frailty in the absence of disability among the older population living in rural communities in South Lebanon. We conducted a cross-sectional population-based study of 400 older adults aged > 65 living in rural and urban communities in South Lebanon. The adults under study gave their consent to fill out a population characteristic sheet and were then screened for frailty using the “Frailty Phenotype.” The population characteristic sheet entailed different risk factors known to be related to frailty. The prevalence of frailty in South Lebanon was found to be 24.5%, with a high prevalence in urban areas as compared to rural areas. The main factors that stood out in rural and urban areas were: age, female gender, number of chronic diseases, number of medications, obesity, depression, and limited access to health services. The findings shed light on poor aging in rural and urban communities in South Lebanon, as evidenced by frailty prevalence. Our findings suggest the need of frailty awareness (by policymakers and the general public), so as to avoid negative consequences. To reduce the healthcare burden, this study recommends that early screening for frailty in primary care be considered! Frailty is a common geriatric syndrome that poses an increased risk of catastrophic declines in health and functional impairment in older adults. Frailty is a condition associated with aging that has been recognized for centuries. Despite gaining global attention, determinants of frailty have remained unmeasured in rural/urban community settings in Lebanon. This study aimed to identify this gap by assessing the prevalence and determinants of frailty in the absence of disability among the older population living in rural communities in South Lebanon.

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Introduction

We are facing a wave of aging, or the so-called “Silver Tsunami” that is expected to hit the world with 2 billion elderly people by the year 2050 (Santini et al., 2015). Lebanon is no exception, as it will be among the first countries in the Arab world to be affected by the demographic change (Sibai et al., 2004).

As a syndrome that affects the elderly, frailty is characterized by an accelerated decline in physiological, social, and/or psychological reserves. Consequently, it leads to disability, morbidity, and mortality. Frailty has always drawn the attention of scientists around the world to determine its prevalence and the associated factors (Buttery et al., 2015). A central point of attention is: "Prevention", which must be assessed and managed in order to prevent the preventable factors (Gu et al., 2009).

Frailty is a high predictor of poor aging (Pegorari & Tavares, 2014; Salem et al., 2014) and has catastrophic effects on the Lebanese government and society. There are several factors that lead to frailty, which differ between countries as well as between rural and urban areas (Moreira & Lourenço, 2013). Frailty cannot be prevented or delayed without knowing and addressing the contributing factors (Ng et al., 2014). In this respect, and to the best of our knowledge, no studies have been carried out in South Lebanon to tackle the frailty issue.

Our study, therefore, aims to determine the prevalence of frailty in rural and urban areas of South Lebanon and to compare the associated factors with frailty in both communities.

Methods

Study Design

A quantitative approach using a descriptive population-based cross-sectional study design was carried out, in order to determine the prevalence of frailty (in percent) among elderly people living in shared apartments in South Lebanon. The study was carried out between April 2017 and August 2017.

Sample Calculation

Lebanon is divided into 8 mohafazats (governorates), see Figure 1. Each of the mohafazats is subdivided into several cazas (districts), yielding a total of 25 cazas. To investigate the prevalence of frailty in South Lebanon, a sample of 400 subjects, consisting of 200 subjects from the Sidon district, with 100 subjects from the city of Sidon (regarded as "urban") and 100 subjects from the villages belonging to the Sidon district (regarded as rural); and 200 subjects from the Nabatiyeh district, with 100 subjects from the city of Nabatiyeh (regarded as "urban") and 100 subjects from the villages belonging to the Nabatiyeh district (regarded as "rural"), were selected. A list of the elderly people living in each of the sampled districts was obtained from municipalities or the local authorities.

The sample was selected by means of probability cluster sampling. For a population of 377,473 elderly people in Lebanon (UNDP, 2008), at least 400 subjects were deemed necessary to establish a 95% confidence level within 5% accuracy, see table 1 below.

Selection Criteria

The criteria for inclusion were as follows: at least 65 years old, lives at home/with relatives, and free from a terminal disease. The criteria for exclusion were as follows: under 65 years old, institutionalized, having a terminal disease, hospitalized, and having a Mini-Mental State Exam (MMSE) of less than 12 years.

Figure 1. Map of Lebanon (Governorates)

Table 1. Confidence level, margin of error, and sample size

	Confidence level = 95%			Confidence level = 99%		
	Margin of error			Margin of error		
Population size	5%	2,5%	1%	5%	2,5%	1%
100	80	94	99	87	96	99
500	217	377	475	285	421	485
1.000	278	606	906	399	727	943
10.000	370	1.332	4.899	622	2.098	6.239
100.000	383	1.513	8.762	659	2.585	14.227
500.000	384	1.532	9.423	663	2.640	16.055
1.000.000	384	1.534	9.512	663	2.647	16.317

Data Collection and Measurements

Due to the possible differences between ages, in terms of educational level, we always obtained verbal consent from participants, taking into account the constant presence of two witnesses.

Information from both clinical measurements and population characteristics was collected. For clinical measurements, we used the frailty phenotype created by Fried to measure frailty. To investigate factors that might contribute to frailty, a selection of factors reported in the literature review with links to frailty was made; these constituted the so-called population characteristics. The frailty phenotype (Fried et al., 2001) is considered the gold standard model for measuring frailty (Nunes et al., 2015) and is most commonly used to assess and measure frailty (Lee et al., 2017).

Variables

Socio-demographic Factors

These included factors such as age, ethnicity, gender, marital status, financial support, availability of health guarantor, educational level, previous or current occupation.

Situational Factors

These included: life events such as physical, sexual, verbal victimization, discriminatory abuse, financial abuse, neglect, physical abuse, psychological and emotional abuse, present or history of homelessness, and incarceration.

Health-related Factors

These included: nutritional status (BMI, waist circumference), presence of chronic diseases (cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, congestive heart failure ... etc.), visual problems, hearing problems, polypharmacy (using five or more medications daily), depression (by means of the geriatric depression scale), loneliness, perception of health, cognitive impairment (according to MMSE), recent hospitalization, recent fall, functional capacity (ADL and IDAL) and urinary incontinence.

Behavioral Factors

These included: smoking, alcohol consumption, physical exercise, and agricultural work involvement.

Resource factors

These included: whom they live with (family, partner, or alone), and social and spiritual engagements (companies, social activities, parties ... etc.)

Environmental factors

These included: area of residence, an area close to pollutants, hygiene and sanitation status.

Statistical Methods and Results

Population characteristics of rural and urban areas were tested by means of a t-test for continuous variables and a Chi-squared test for categorical variables. The prevalence of frailty was analyzed by means of the Chi-square test. Statistical analysis was performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 22.

About one-third of the sample consisted of elderly people aged 65 to 70 years old, out of whom 38.0% live in rural areas and 32.5% in urban areas.

The relationship between the socioeconomic factors and frailty is provided in Table 2. In urban areas, most of the non-frail elderly are males aged 65 to 70 years, are married, have median financial support and a health guarantor, and are well educated. This association is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) except for marital status and the availability of health guarantor ($p > 0.05$). On the other hand, in rural areas, non-frail elderly are also males aged 65-70 years, are married, have median financial support and health guarantor, and are well educated. This association is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) except for the availability of a health guarantor ($p > 0.05$).

Table 2. Distribution of factors by frailty and residence

Factor	Urban			Sig.	Rural			Sig.
	Non-Frail n (%)	Pre-Frail n (%)	Frail n (%)		Non-Frail n (%)	Pre-Frail n (%)	Frail n (%)	
Age (in years)				$\chi^2 = 35.54$				$\chi^2 = 39.34$
[65-70]	23 (65.7%)	36 (33.3%)	6 (10.5%)	$p < 0.0001$	30 (61.2%)	38 (34.5%)	8 (19.5%)	$p < 0.0001$
[70-75]	8 (22.9%)	34 (31.5%)	17 (29.8%)		19 (38.8%)	37 (33.6%)	11 (26.8%)	
[75-80]	4 (11.4%)	21 (19.4%)	13 (22.8%)		0 (0.0%)	26 (23.6%)	17 (41.5%)	
80 and above	0 (0.0%)	17 (15.7%)	21 (36.8%)		0 (0.0%)	9 (8.2%)	5 (12.2%)	
Gender				$\chi^2 = 34.80$				$\chi^2 = 15.93$
Male	30 (85.7%)	63 (58.3%)	14 (24.6%)	$p < 0.0001$	38 (77.6%)	58 (52.7%)	15 (36.6%)	$p < 0.0001$
Female	5 (14.3%)	45 (41.7%)	43 (75.4%)		11 (22.4%)	52 (47.3%)	26 (63.4%)	
Marital Status				$\chi^2 = 8.78$				$\chi^2 = 27.18$
Married	28 (80.0%)	53 (49.1%)	19 (33.3%)	$p = 0.187$	40 (81.6%)	71 (64.5%)	26 (63.4%)	$p < 0.0001$
Widowed	4 (11.4%)	39 (36.1%)	32 (56.1%)		8 (16.3%)	34 (30.9%)	14 (34.1%)	
Divorced	1 (2.9%)	11 (10.2%)	1 (1.8%)		0 (0.0%)	4 (3.6%)	0 (0.0%)	
Single	2 (5.7%)	5 (4.6%)	5 (8.8%)		1 (2.4%)	1 (0.9%)	1 (2.4%)	

Table 2 (cont.): Distribution of factors by frailty and residence

Financial Support				$\chi^2=12.81$				$\chi^2=16.89$
<i>Unsatisfactory</i>	2 (5.7%)	5 (4.6%)	11 (19.3%)	$p=0.012$	0 (0.0%)	10 (9.1%)	10 (24.4%)	$p=0.002$
<i>Median</i>	18 (51.4%)	57 (52.8%)	19 (33.3%)		40 (81.6%)	76 (69.1%)	21 (51.2%)	
<i>Satisfactory</i>	15 (42.9%)	46 (42.6%)	27 (47.4%)		9 (18.4%)	24 (21.8%)	10 (24.4%)	
Availability of Health Guarantor				$\chi^2=2.82$				$\chi^2=3.48$
<i>Yes</i>	22 (62.9%)	60 (55.6%)	26 (45.6%)	$p=0.244$	27 (55.1%)	61 (55.5%)	16 (39.0%)	$p=0.175$
<i>No</i>	13 (37.1%)	48 (44.4%)	31 (54.4%)		22 (44.9%)	49 (44.5%)	25 (61.0%)	
Educational level				$\chi^2=38.03$				$\chi^2=29.04$
<i>Illiterate</i>	3 (22.9%)	16 (14.8%)	11 (19.3%)	$p<0.0001$	0 (0.0%)	32 (29.1%)	10 (24.4%)	$p=0.001$
<i>Did not complete elementary school</i>	8 (22.9%)	11 (10.2%)	11 (19.3%)		8 (16.3%)	20 (18.2%)	10 (24.4%)	
<i>Completed elementary school</i>	1 (2.9%)	22 (20.4%)	20 (35.1%)		16 (32.7%)	34 (30.9%)	11 (26.8%)	
<i>Did not complete high school</i>	0 (0.0%)	15 (13.9%)	6 (10.5%)		12 (24.5%)	11 (10.0%)	8 (19.5%)	
<i>Completed high school</i>	1 (2.9%)	17 (15.7%)	7 (12.3%)		10 (20.4%)	9 (8.2%)	1 (2.4%)	
<i>Completed university</i>	13 (37.1%)	27 (25.0%)	2 (3.5%)		3 (6.1%)	4 (3.6%)	1 (2.4%)	

Discussion

In the surveyed elderly population, frailty accounted for 24.5%, pre-frailty for 54.5%, and non-frailty for 21%. In rural areas, the percentages were as follows: 20.5% were frail, 55% were pre-frail and 24.5% were non-frail, as compared to 28.5% who were frail, 54% who were pre-frail, and 17.5% who were non-frail in urban areas. Even though the prevalence of frailty was higher in urban areas as compared to rural areas, the difference was not statistically significant ($p>0.05$). This is consistent with the results of other studies that noted that urban residents have higher frailty levels than rural residents, particularly amongst women (Gu et al., 2009).

With respect to the frailty phenotype that consists of 5 components: unintentional weight loss, exhaustion, low energy expenditure, weak grip strength, and walk time, no statistically significant differences were found between rural and urban areas concerning weak grip strength and walk time. With respect to the ones who live in urban areas, they have more unintentional weight loss as compared to 18% in rural areas ($p<0.05$); 39.5% suffer exhaustion as compared to 30% who live in rural areas, 29% have low energy expenditure as compared to 20% who live in rural areas. The association between unintentional weight loss, exhaustion, low energy expenditure, and the environment (urban/rural) was found to be statistically significant ($p<0.05$). Weak grip strength accounted for the

highest percentage (51.5%) amongst the participants who met one or more of the Fried Criteria for Frailty in both rural and urban areas. This outcome coincides with the results of a study conducted in rural Korea where the weakness component accounted for 50.9% (Jung et al., 2016). On the other hand, unintentional weight loss accounted for the lowest percentage (22.5%) in rural and urban areas. Both percentages of weakness and weight loss contradict the results of a study conducted in rural Andes Mountains (Curcio et al., 2014).

Regarding the frailty status of elderly people living in urban areas and their association with socioeconomic factors, it was found that 36.8% of frail people are aged 80 years and over as compared to 33% of pre-frail ones aged 65 to 70 years old and 65.7% of non-frail ones aged 65 to 70 years. This outcome shows that the majority of young elderly are non-frail. On the other hand, 41.5% of frail elderly who live in rural areas are between 75 and 80 years old and 61.2% of the non-frail ones are aged 65 to 70 years. The association between the frailty status and age is statistically significant. This is consistent with the results of other studies that found that frailty increases with age for both women and men (Carneiro et al., 2016; Gu et al., 2009; Mello et al., 2014; Pegorari & Tavares, 2014; Runzer-Colmenares et al., 2014). This can be explained by the fact that advanced age was a risk factor for decreased self-care ability. Physical activity decreases later in life, which may be due to a lack of opportunities or encouragement. The frequency of physical activity was the strongest positive factor that explained self-care ability amongst the elderly population. In addition, food preparation was found to be a positive factor in self-sufficiency in rural areas; family support negatively affected self-sufficiency.

Concerning the gender of the participants, women were found to be frailer than men, with men being non-frail in both rural and urban areas. The association between frailty and gender was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). These results agree with the results of other studies (Abdulraheem et al., 2011; Jung et al., 2016; Mello et al., 2014; Pegorari & Tavares, 2014; Woo et al., 2015).

Our findings revealed that the prevalence of frailty in rural areas was 63.4% for women and 36.6% for men. This percentage is higher than the prevalence of frailty amongst rural women (44.6%), as reported in an AMEL (Aging and Malnutrition in Elderly Lebanese) study in rural Lebanon. The same applies to rural men where the same study found that the prevalence of frailty amongst rural men was 28.1%. This difference may be related to the different tools used for frailty screening, as well as to the different areas of residence and sample sizes of the population (Boulos et al., 2013).

More than half of frail older urban residents (56.1%) were widowed, whereas 80% of the non-frail ones were married. On the other hand, 63.4% of frail rural residents were married and 81.6% of non-frail rural ones were married. The association between marital status and frailty was found to be significant in rural areas but not in urban areas.

Moreover, the relationship between financial support and frailty was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This outcome coincides with the results of other studies that noted that being married is associated with a lower risk of frailty (Woo et al., 2015). Amongst frail rural residents, 51.2% had median financial support as compared to 81.6% for the non-frail ones. Amongst the urban frail elderly, 47.4% noted that their financial support was satisfactory; 51.4% of the non-frail ones noted that they have median financial support. Most of the respondents regarded their financial support as being median to satisfactory. Even though there was a difference between frailty status and the availability of a guarantor, the difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Most of the ones who were frail did not have a health guarantor; the majority of those who were not frail had a health guarantor.

Moreover, the relationship between educational level and frailty status amongst the elderly who live in urban and rural areas was statistically significant. In rural areas, most of the frail elderly people were less educated; for the non-frail elderly people, they were more educated. This outcome coincides with the results noted in the literature (Pegorari & Tavares, 2014).

Regarding the situational factors, there was a statistically significant difference between frailty status and the occurrence of events that were accompanied by physical, sexual, emotional, verbal, and financial abuse ($p < 0.05$). Most of the non-frail elderly people who resided in urban areas (91.4%) and rural areas (91.8%) did not have such life events; this could be linked to the fear of reporting such abuses. Regarding the history of homelessness and its relationship with frailty status, there was no significant statistical association ($p > 0.05$) amongst the elderly people who lived in rural and urban areas. Regarding the association between incarceration and frailty status, there was no statistically significant association in rural areas; however, the association was found to be significant in urban areas. It should be noted here that 85.7% of the non-frail ones were never incarcerated. In general, homeless individuals are more apt to become frail. In our study, the number of homeless people was too low to draw any reliable conclusions; future studies will eventually target these individuals.

The health-related factors including BMI, waist circumference, number of chronic diseases, visual problems, hearing problems, polypharmacy, depression status, loneliness, perception of health, cognitive impairment, MMSE, history of recent hospitalization, history of recent fall, urinary incontinence, and level of independence were assessed by means of ADL (Activities of Daily Living) and IADL (Instrumental Activities of Daily Living).

The results of the present study revealed that the association between BMI, number of chronic diseases, presence of visual problems, presence of polypharmacy, depression status, loneliness, perception of health, cognitive impairment, MMSE, history of recent hospitalization, history of recent fall, presence of urinary incontinence, level of functional capacity (ADL, IADL) and frailty status were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) in both urban and rural areas, besides hearing problems in rural areas but not in urban areas. Those who are frail, obese, have 3 diseases and more and have visual problems, tend to take more than 4 drugs. They are depressed ($GDS > 5$) and lonely, perceive their health as poor, have cognitive impairment from moderate to mild, and had been recently hospitalized (43.9%), 40.3% had a recent fall, 19.3% had urinary incontinence, 49.1% were dependent according to ADL and 63.2% were dependent according to IADL in urban areas. In rural areas, those who are frail, are obese, have one to two chronic diseases, have visual problems, take more than four drugs, depressed (39.0%), lonely (46.3%), perceive their health as being average, have cognitive problems from mild to questionably significant (41.5%), had been recently hospitalized (41.5%), had a recent fall (26.8%), had urinary incontinence (39%), were dependent according to ADL (29.3%) and 36.6% were dependent based on IADL.

The elderly people under study avoided going outside for fear of falling; this fear affected their daily activities and functional capacity, thus increasing the risk of frailty (Çakmur, 2015). Most of the frail Lebanese elderly respondents were obese, in both rural and urban areas. The association of frailty and obesity was not surprising, as revealed in other studies too (Mello et al., 2014; Ng et al., 2014). Noteworthy is that the BMI mean value in our studied population was 28.37 kg/m^2 and the mean waist circumference was 93.08 cm. This certainly increases the risks of chronic diseases, cardiovascular diseases, and diabetes (Wang et al., 2005).

With respect to the association between behavioral factors and frailty status, there was a statistically significant association between frailty status and smoking status, physical exercises, and agricultural work engagement in rural areas, with the exception of alcohol consumption. On the other hand, with respect to the association between behavioral factors and frailty status, there was a statistically

significant association between frailty status and smoking status, physical exercises, and alcohol consumption in urban areas, with the exception of agricultural work engagement. Concerning urban non-frail elderly people, 62.9% currently smoke, 80.0% do not consume alcohol, 48.6% do physical exercises, and 94.3% do not engage in agricultural work. However, regarding rural non-frail elderly people, 63.3% do not smoke, 83.7% do not consume alcohol, 65.3% do physical exercises, and 59.2% engage in agricultural work. These results clearly show that being physically inactive is a risk factor faced by the urban population, coupled with the fact that they do not engage in agricultural activities. The relationship between smoking, alcohol use, physical inactivity, and frailty may be bi-directional, in that frailty itself may result in avoidance of smoking, alcohol, and physical inactivity (Woo et al., 2015).

Moreover, there is a significant association between resource factors and the frailty status in rural areas. In urban areas, there was no significant correlation between the people they live with and the frailty status. Most rural frail elderly people live with a partner, and nearly one-third have social and spiritual engagements. On the other hand, 49.1% of frail urban elderly people live with a family member and 71.9% of these do not have social and spiritual engagements. It is important to note that for the non-frail urban elderly people, more than half live with a partner, and 85.7% have social and spiritual engagements. This is similar to the results of other studies that found that religious participation protected against frailty perhaps because of reduced psychological distress and improved spiritual coping, social support, or a more generalized and positive belief system (Gu et al., 2009). Finally, there was no significant association between environmental factors and the frailty status in urban areas, where hygiene and sanitation are regarded as being good. On the other hand, the same goes for the rural population.

Conclusions

The prevalence of frailty amongst Lebanese rural elderly people is less than that in urban areas due principally to daily agricultural works in rural areas, which satisfy physical activities participation.

The studied population in this work is between 65 and 75 years old; with more than half being males, 59.2% married, 32.8% widowed, 57.8% perceived their financial support as median, 53% had a health guarantor and more than half had completed elementary education. Only 13.8% had life events that were accompanied by abuse, 4.2% had a history of homelessness and 3% had been incarcerated at one point in time.

The socioeconomic factors revealed that three-quarters of the population had one to two chronic diseases, 38.8% had visual problems, 18.2% had hearing problems, 43% took more than four drugs, 29.8% were lonely, 39% perceived their health as being average, 16.2% had a cognitive impairment, 23.5% experienced a recent hospitalization, 13% experienced a recent fall, 11% had urinary incontinence, 10.2% had dependence according to ADL and 14.8% were dependent according to IADL. Moreover, the mean BMI in our sample was 28.37 kg/m², with 28% being obese and 49.25% being overweight; with a mean waist circumference of 93.08 cm. The mean GDS (Geriatric Depression Scale) was 4.28, with 24.75% being depressed; the mean MMSE was 26.5, with 72.5% were questionably significant but not severe.

Regarding the behavioral factors, 43.2% were nonsmokers and 37% were smokers; only 9.8% drank alcohol; about one-third (30.5%) engaged in physical exercises; and 28% engaged in agricultural work engagement, of whom 51.5% lived in rural areas.

More than half of the sample of respondents lived with a partner and 63.2% had social and spiritual engagements. The majority (96.5%) of respondents lived in areas not too close to pollutants (wastes, factories, etc.) where good hygiene and sanitation were in effect.

The frailty status revealed that 24.5% were frail, 54.5% were pre-frail and 21% were non-frail. The factors associated with frailty were socioeconomic factors, situational, health-related, behavioral, resource, and environmental factors. The frail elderly population was mostly people 80 years and over, females, mostly widowed, without a health guarantor and a low educational level. The non-frail elderly people did not experience life events like homelessness or incarceration.

Most of the frail elderly people were obese, with more than 2 chronic diseases, with visual problems, being depressed and consumed more than four drugs, felt lonely, perceived their health as being poor; 28.1% had moderate MMSE, dependent, with a history of a recent hospitalization. Most of the frail elderly people did not smoke, did not consume alcohol, did not engage in physical exercises, and were not involved in agricultural work. Most of the frail elderly people lived with a family member, and 85.7% of the non-frail people did engage in social and spiritual activities. The frail and non-frail population lived in areas with good hygiene and sanitation and far from pollutants (wastes, factories, etc ...)

Our findings demonstrate that psychosocial factors play a somewhat significant role in the severity of frailty and should remain an important factor in medical practice and public health interventions.

It is plausible that individuals may live to age 100 or beyond and remain relatively healthy by adhering to healthy lifestyles and avoiding identifiable risks. One key to healthy longevity is the prevention or delay of frailty and the facilitation of recovery from frailty via medical interventions or treatments.

The aging population in Lebanon is projected to be accompanied by increasing frailty and there is a need to focus on measures to reduce the frailty burden. The situation for the rural population is different: they have a shorter life expectancy and a lower prevalence of frailty, resulting in the lowest frailty burden.

Study Limitations

The study had several limitations. To begin with, the nature of the study as cross-sectional prevented us from examining the cause-and-effect between frailty and the associated factors in urban and rural areas in South Lebanon. A second issue is that we did not take into consideration the elderly people who were taking antidepressants; thus, this could have affected the Geriatric Depression scale score and consequently the prevalence of depression in our sample. A third limitation was that the Fried Phenotype and our developed population characteristics sheet had several questions that were self-reported; given the ages of the participants, recall bias could have occurred. Finally, the handgrip was measured using a dynamometer shipped from china from a company called “KYTD DIGITAL”, model number “EH101”. Even though we have carried out a daily calibration of the device, a margin of error could have resulted.

Ethical concerns

This study was conducted under ethical clearance from the Lebanese University, Faculty of Public Health, Branch 5. We declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Generalizability

This study reflects some extent on the frailty situation in South Lebanon. It opens the doors for future studies about the subject matter in order to gain a better perspective of the true situation of frailty in the whole of Lebanon.

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